

Factorial Theorem: An Alternative to Gamma Function

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Abstract: This paper presents the factorial theorem that is used to compute the factorial for positive real number, which is greater than or equal to 1. The factorial theorem is an alternative to the gamma function.

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1. Introduction

In general, the factorial [1-12] for positive integer n , denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n . For example, $5! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 720$. Similarly, we can find the value of factorial for a positive real number using factorials theorems that are proved in this article. The factorial theorem introduced in the article is an alternative to the gamma function.

The gamma function [13, 14] is a generalization of the factorial function, introduced by the Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler in the 18th century.

$$\Gamma(n+1) = n(n-1)! = n\Gamma(n). \\ \Gamma(1) = 0! = 1; \Gamma(2) = 1! = 1; \Gamma(3) = 2! = 2.$$

$$\text{Also, } \Gamma(r) = (r-1)! = \int_0^{\infty} t^{r-1} e^{-t} dt.$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{2} - 1\right)! = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

2. Error in Calculation using Gamma Function

It is understood that $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \sqrt{\pi} \approx 1.77245385091$,

but $\Gamma(3) > \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) > \Gamma(2)$, which is a contradiction.

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{3}{2} - 1\right)\left(\frac{3}{2} - 1 - 1\right)! = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}.$$

So, $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ is not true and also calculating the value of $\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)$ using $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ can not be true.

From these results, it is concluded that the calculated values using $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ are not true.

3. Factorial Theorem

Theorem 2.1: $(x+1)! = x! + \{(x+1)! - x!\}$, where $x \geq 0$.

Proof:

$$x! + \{(x+1)! - x!\} = x! + \{x!(x+1) - x!\} = x! + x!(x) = x!\{1+x\} = (x+1)!, (x \geq 0).$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Let us verify the theorem with positive real numbers.

$$(x + 1)! = x! + \{(x + 1)! - x!\} = x! + (0.64)\{(x + 1)! - x!\} + (0.36)\{(x + 1)! - x!\}$$

$$x! + (0.64 + 0.36)\{(x + 1)! - x!\} = x! + \{(x + 1)! - x!\}.$$

Theorem 2.2: $y! = (y + 1)! - \{(y + 1)! - y!\}$, where $y \geq 1$.

Proof:

$$(y + 1)! - \{(y + 1)! - y!\} = y! (y + 1) - \{y! (y + 1) - y!\}$$

$$= y! (y + 1) - y! (y) = y! (y + 1 - y) = y!, (y \geq 1).$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Let us verify the theorem with positive real numbers.

$$y! = (y + 1)! - \{(y + 1)! - y!\}$$

$$= (y + 1)! - (1 - 0.64)\{(y + 1)! - y!\} - (1 - 0.36)\{(y + 1)! - y!\}$$

$$= (y + 1)! - (0.36)\{(y + 1)! - y!\} - (0.64)\{(y + 1)! - y!\}$$

$$= (y + 1)! - \{(y + 1)! - y!\}.$$

4. Factorial for Positive Real number

Let $z = i.f$ be a positive real number, where i is an integer part, f is the decimal or fractional part, and $z \geq 1$. The factorial function to positive real number is established from the perspective of the above theorems as follows:

$$z! = (i.f)! = i! + (0.f)\{(i + 1)! - i!\}.$$

For examples,

$$(1.0)! = 1! + (0.0)\{(i + 1)! - i!\} = 1 + 0 = 1.$$

$$(4.6)! = 4! + (0.6)(5! - 4!) = 24 + (0.6)(120 - 24) = 81.6.$$

The gamma function calculator [15] computes the factorial function $(4.6)!$ as follows:

$$\Gamma(5.6) = (5.6 - 1)! = (4.6)! = 61.5.$$

5. Factorial for Rational and Irrational numbers

If $\frac{p}{q}, (q \neq 0) = i\frac{f}{q}$ is a common rational number, where $\frac{p}{q} \geq 1, f < q$, & i is an integer.

$$\text{Then, } \left(\frac{p}{q}\right)! = i! + \left(\frac{f}{q}\right)\{(i + 1)! - i!\}.$$

For examples,

$$1! = \left(1\frac{0}{1}\right)! = 1! + \left(\frac{0}{1}\right)\{(1 + 1)! - 1!\} = 1 + 0 = 1.$$

$$\left(\frac{14}{4}\right)! = \left(3\frac{2}{4}\right)! = 3! + \left(\frac{2}{4}\right)(4! - 3!) = 6 + 9 = 15.$$

Let \sqrt{x} be an irrational number, where $\sqrt{x} \geq 1$. If i is the integer part on \sqrt{x} .

$$\text{Then, } (\sqrt{x})! = i! + \sqrt{x}\{(i + 1)! - i!\} - i\{(i + 1)! - i!\}.$$

For examples,

$$(\sqrt{1})! = 1! + \sqrt{1}(2! - 1! - 1(2! - 1!)) = 1 + 1 - 1 = 1.$$

$$(\sqrt{15})! = 3! + \sqrt{15}(4! - 3!) - 3(4! - 3!).$$

$$(119)! = 10! + \sqrt{119}(11! - 10!) - 10(11! - 10!).$$

6. Conclusion

In this article, factorial theorem for positive real numbers has been introduced and it is an alternative to the gamma function. This result can be used as an application in computing and mathematical sciences including probability and statistics.

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